

Challenges of Teachers on Modular Learning: Basis for Development Plan

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Abstract:

The descriptive study focused on teachers' challenges in modular learning, a learning modality adopted by Manjuyod National High School during the pandemic. In general, it aimed to determine the degree of challenges teachers encountered in modular learning at Manjuyod National High School. Needed data came from Junior High School teachers of the above research environment using a self-made data-gathering instrument that has passed the exhaustive tests of validity and reliability. Initial findings showed that most respondents were senior females with longer lengths of service. Subsequent analysis showed a moderate level of challenges in the areas of distribution, retrieval, and feedback-giving. When grouped according to age, sex, and length of service, the level of challenges teachers experienced in modular learning was likewise moderate. Moreover, no significant difference exists in teachers' challenges with modular learning in all areas and demographic variables earlier mentioned. From the foregoing results, his study concludes that teachers were having problems with modular learning, which was an entirely new experience for teachers and school administrators alike. This study calls for ample funds and preparation of learning materials and a serious consideration of the geographical location in the crafting of an annual development plan for schools in the far-flung areas.

Keywords: Challenges of Teachers, modular learning, distribution, retrieval and feedback giving.

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

There were many learning modalities for the DepEd to adopt to continue the teaching-learning program; one is distance learning. Distance learning is a way of learning without physical interaction between the instructor and the learner. Learning materials are sent online or through self-learning kits or modules to the learners. DepEd Memorandum DM-CI-2020-00162 suggests strategies for implementing distance learning delivery modalities (DLDM) for the school year 2020-2021. The memorandum was issued following the president's directive that there will be no face-to-face classes unless there is a vaccine for COVID-19. According to the memo, distance learning may be implemented in different modalities. It may be through modular distance learning (either printed or digital), Online Distance Learning, TV-Video/Radio-based Instruction, or blended distance learning. DepEd Order No. 007, s. 2020 otherwise known as School Calendar and Activities for School Year 2020-2021, states that under the supervision of ROs and SDOs, are authorized to decide on the specific DLDM which may be deemed appropriate in their context.

Recently, there has been growing interest in education amidst COVID-19. The president decided to suspend face-to-face classes until there was a vaccine. This situation challenged DepEd. With the suspension of face-to-face classes, the adoption of a new modality of teaching could be a challenge to teachers and learners. There are many things to consider in adopting a new modality, especially during this pandemic, when DepEd stakeholders are still trying to adjust from everyday life to a new normal life. Though other schools have already been using distance learning, this is the first time that DepEd would try to adopt such modalities.

Such a scenario prompts the researcher to find out the challenges of the junior high school teachers on distance learning and its relation to learners' Academic Performance in Manjuyod National High School to prepare, adapt, create, or reinvent certain ways of methods of teaching.

Current State of Knowledge

Joyce (2020), in her article about Stackable, Modular Learning: Education Built for the Future of Work, pointed out that traditional education requires significant financial and opportunity costs, sometimes without a clear return. Joyce wrote that modular learning reduces the cycle time of learning. She also pointed out that modular learning has the same or better outcome than traditional learning because of its flexibility, personalized spacing, and instant feedback. One problem with modular learning is the delivery of the modules to very remote communities. DepEd Regional Office 3 (2020) addresses this problem by delivering printed format to schools that are located in coastal areas, far-flung provinces, and communities without access to the Internet or electricity. For households with gadgets and devices, the Department has announced that SLMs can also be accessed online or offline.

Distance learning already exists even before the peak of the Internet. It has dramatically evolved, catering to the needs of the norm. Many different distance learning types were already introduced, which may be synchronous or asynchronous. Campus Explorer (2019) enumerated four types of distance learning; these are Open scheduled online courses, where students are provided with internet-based textbooks, emails, and bulletin boards for the student to finish a course; hybrid distance learning, wherein a learner is scheduled to meet with the teacher in a particular online chatroom; computer-based distance learning where students are scheduled for a class in a computer laboratory or a classroom; and fixed time online courses which are more strict because mandatory live chats are required.

Folsom (2020) suggested principles to support educators and students in tackling distance learning amidst the pandemic. First is to change the learning goals and the learning process since the lives of the students and even the educators are different from the pre-pandemic time, and so norms are different now. Second, design learning activities for the distance learning environment. Educators must focus on activities that maximize learner engagement and avoid barriers. Third, prepare for students' upcoming challenges. This means that educators must be prepared that certain student problems may arise during distance learning, and it is essential for educators to respond with empathy. Fourth, investigate institutional policies in order for the stakeholders to be guided in the course of the learning experiences and to avoid mis enrollment in courses. The last one is to model a growth mindset where if the distance learning plans fail, teach the students how to respond to failure and get back up.

Omonovich et al. (2020), in their study about the use of modular technology in education, discuss the issues and the purpose of modular education as well as the problems of teachers in creating a module. They found out that modular training depends not only on the level of the teacher but also on the student's mastery level. They also found out that in creating a module, one must have pedagogical experience, and hard work, which requires a lot of research.

Mitrofanova et al. (2020) defined modular education as an autonomous set of studying and training materials that consist of information, practical, and control components for the discipline and are created by teaching staff according to the thematic elements of subjects claimed to the professional curriculums. Mitrofanova et al. suggested that modular education, with its complete and interactive multimedia products, can solve educational issues.

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is anchored on Michael Moore's Transactional Distance Theory. This theory met the needs of teaching and learning that went on outside the traditional classroom face-to-face learning. Transactional distance is the cognitive space between teachers and learners in a distance education setting. There are three main components of transactional distance theory. The first one is Dialogue. It is defined as the interplay of words, actions, ideas, and any other interactions between teachers and learners. Second, Structure, or the organized framework of a distance learning course. It describes the extent to which an educational program can accommodate or be responsive to the learners' individual needs. Third is learner autonomy which is the extent to which the learner determines the goals, learning experiences, and evaluation decisions of the program.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the degree of challenges encountered by teachers on modular learning at Manjuyod National High School for the school year 2020-2021 as a basis for a development plan. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions: 1) the degree of challenges encountered in modular learning according to distribution, retrieval and feedback giving; 2) the degree of challenges encountered by teachers in modular learning when grouped according to the aforementioned variables; and, 3) the significant difference in the degree

of challenges encountered by teachers on modular learning when they are grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Methodology

This section presents the research design used, the locale, the subjects, the respondents of the study, the research instrument used, the validity and reliability of the research instrument, the conduct of the study, the procedure in the analysis of the data relative to the specific objective and the statistical tool used in the study.

Research Design

This study will utilize the descriptive method of research using the survey tool employed in gathering data needed for the study. According to Best and Khan (2013), descriptive design seeks "what is" and emphasizes discovering ideas and insights that may affect the development of generalizations, principles, or theories. It focuses on the present conditions, which aims for new truths that could help one make adequate and accurate interpretations of the data collected. The descriptive research design will be the most appropriate to determine the degree of challenges teachers face on modular learning as the basis for a development plan to address related problems on modular learning that influence such.

Respondents

Respondents of the study will be the Junior High School Teachers of Manjuyod National High School during the school year 2020-2021, composed of 50 Junior High School Teachers and will be used as the total population of the study.

Instruments

The researcher gathered the needed data for this study by constructing a research-made survey questionnaire to determine the level of job satisfaction and their level of performance. It was subjected to validity (4.78-excellent) and reliability (0.943-Acceptable). All of them were interpreted as worthy and good, respectively. To determine the level of challenges for junior high school teachers on distance learning, the survey questionnaire will have two parts. Part I of the questionnaire contains the profile of the teacher respondents, such as age, length of service, and highest educational attainment. Part II will be composed of survey items about the distribution of the module, retrieval of the module, and feedback given. The responses will be interpreted using a five-point Likert scale as follows: Always (5), Oftentimes (4), Sometimes (3), Seldom (2), and Almost Never (1).

Data Gathering Procedure

Upon the panel members' approval on the final copy of the survey questionnaire, the researcher will submit them for validation by members of the jury experts. This will also be tested for reliability. The researcher will ask permission from the school principal for the administration of the survey instrument. The purpose of the study will be explained to them. After permission is secured and granted, enough copies of the survey questionnaire will be reproduced. The researcher will personally conduct the questionnaires to the respondents or through Google Forms. Questionnaires will be gathered right after answering. Then the data gathered from the respondents will be tallied and tabulated using the appropriate statistical tools with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and the assigned statistician.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective no. 1 also used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine teachers' challenges in three areas of concern: distribution, retrieval, and feedback-giving.

Objective no. 2 also used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the degree of challenges of teachers on modular learning when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective no. 3 used the comparative analytical scheme and the Mann-Whitney U test to determine the significant difference in the degree of challenges teachers encounter in modular learning when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

Ethical Considerations

The participants' rights were provided, in which they have to understand that their responses will be kept confidential and made available only to the researchers. No one was able to identify the participants when the results were reported, and the participant's name did not appear anywhere in the written report. The participants were made to understand that the consent form was kept separate from the data records to ensure confidentiality.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered in connection with the objectives of the study and analyses of these data facilitated by the identified appropriate statistical tools. It interprets the results derived from the analyses.

Table 1
Degree of Challenges Encountered by Teachers on Modular Learning

ITEMS	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
A. Distribution		
1. Modules were not readily available for teachers to download.	3.18	Moderate Degree
2. Adequate funds were not provided in preparing the modules.	3.14	Moderate Degree
3. Materials for printing the modules were not enough.	2.96	Moderate Degree
4. Insufficient time was given to print the modules.	3.06	Moderate Degree
5. Not enough modules were produced for distribution.	3.02	Moderate Degree
6. Parents/ guardians did not observe minimum health protocols during module distribution.	3.00	Moderate Degree
7. Parents/guardians did not pick up modules on time.	3.26	Moderate Degree
8. Parents/guardians lack interest in picking up the modules.	3.00	Moderate Degree
9. Parents/ guardians did not follow room procedures prepared by the teacher in distributing the modules.	3.08	Moderate Degree
10. Modules were not disinfected before distribution.	3.14	Moderate Degree
Sub-mean	3.08	Moderate Degree
B. Retrieval		
1. Parents/guardians did not return the modules on time.	3.16	Moderate Degree
2. Parents/guardians did not return outputs on time.	3.20	Moderate Degree
3. Modules were not returned the same way it was distributed.	3.26	Moderate Degree
4. Modules were in bad condition upon retrieval.	3.20	Moderate Degree
5. Parents/ guardians did not follow the minimum health protocol in returning the modules.	3.06	Moderate Degree
6. Learners did not answer some of the activities in the module.	3.34	Moderate Degree
7. The teacher did not follow up with the learners whose modules were not returned on time.	2.84	Moderate Degree
8. Parents/ guardians did not follow the classroom procedures the teacher/adviser set in returning the modules.	3.00	Moderate Degree
9. The teacher did not disinfect the modules upon retrieval.	3.00	Moderate Degree
10. There is a fear that the module is contaminated with Covid-19 upon retrieval	3.30	Moderate Degree
Sub-mean	3.14	Moderate Degree
C. Feedback Giving		
1. Parents/guardians were not active in asking questions about the module.	3.16	Moderate Degree
2. Parents/guardians did not inform the teacher of their learners' progress.	3.24	Moderate Degree
3. Parents/guardians did not attend homeroom PTA meetings.	3.02	Moderate Degree
4. Parents/guardians did not ask the teacher for clarifications about certain topics in the module.	3.12	Moderate Degree
5. Parents/guardians and the learners did not ask the teacher about unclear topics in the module.	3.24	Moderate Degree
6. The learners did not answer the modules by themselves.	3.40	Moderate Degree
7. Parents/guardians did not raise concerns about contracting covid 19 during the distribution and retrieval of the module.	3.50	High Degree
8. Parents/guardians had difficulty explaining the lessons to the learners.	3.60	High Degree
9. Parents/guardians complained about the schedule of the distribution and retrieval of modules.	3.16	Moderate Degree
10. Parents/guardians did not discuss intervention strategies to strengthen their child's learning with the teacher.	3.38	Moderate Degree
Sub-mean	3.28	Moderate Degree
Overall mean	3.17	Moderate Degree

Table 1 shows the degree of challenges encountered by teachers with modular Learning. Item no. 7 under Distribution, got the highest mean score of 3.26, interpreted as "moderate degree." This means that one factor that created an obstacle for teachers in distributing the modules was parents' tardiness in picking up the modules from the teachers. Parents may be more concerned about their livelihood than picking up their modules. According to (Dowling 2018), working parents have two jobs. One is their work putting food on their table, and the other is

supporting their children's educational needs. With these two jobs, parents may have difficulty juggling their responsibilities.

Item no. 10 under Retrieval, got the highest mean score of 3.30, interpreted as "moderate degree." This means that teachers are concerned with their safety, especially in retrieving the modules due to possible transmission of the virus. (Tajouri 2020) mentioned that virus transmission can be made possible through objects. Learning materials are no exemption in possible virus transmission.

Item no. 8 under Feedback Giving, got the highest mean score of 3.60, interpreted as "high degree." This means that parents/guardians pose a challenge for the teachers in modular learning because the parents/guardians are the ones that help their children in teaching the lesson at home. (Wadley 2020), in his findings, parents were not ready for distance learning. Parents were overwhelmed with their responsibility to act as teachers to their children.

Table 2

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Teachers on Modular Learning in the Area of Distribution When Grouped According to Age

Areas	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
A. Distribution				
1. Modules were not readily available for teachers to download.	3.13	Moderate Degree	3.23	Moderate Degree
2. Adequate funds were not provided in preparing the modules.	3.08	Moderate Degree	3.19	Moderate Degree
3. Materials for printing the modules were not enough.	3.00	Moderate Degree	2.92	Moderate Degree
4. Insufficient time was given to print the modules.	3.04	Moderate Degree	3.08	Moderate Degree
5. Not enough modules were produced for distribution.	2.96	Moderate Degree	3.08	Moderate Degree
6. Parents/ guardians did not observe minimum health protocols during module distribution.	3.00	Moderate Degree	3.00	Moderate Degree
7. Parents/guardians did not pick up modules on time.	3.25	Moderate Degree	3.27	Moderate Degree
8. Parents/guardians lack interest in picking up the modules.	2.83	Moderate Degree	3.15	Moderate Degree
9. Parents/ guardians did not follow room procedures prepared by the teacher in distributing the modules.	3.04	Moderate Degree	3.12	Moderate Degree
10. Modules were not disinfected before distribution.	3.29	Moderate Degree	3.00	Moderate Degree
Sub-mean	3.06	Moderate Degree	3.10	Moderate Degree

Table 2 shows the degree of challenges encountered by teachers on modular learning in the area of distribution when grouped according to age. Item no. 10 got the highest mean score of 3.29 in the younger group, while item no. 7, got the highest mean score of 3.27 for the older group. Both are interpreted as "moderate degree." The overall mean score for the younger group is 3.06, while the overall mean score for the older group is 3.10, and both are interpreted as "moderate degree." This means that teachers are concerned with parents not following the scheduled time for picking up the modules and also with the health protocols for distributing the modules.

Table 3

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Teachers on Modular Learning in the Area of Retrieval When Grouped According to Age

Areas	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
B. Retrieval				
1. Parents/guardians did not return the modules on time.	3.08	Moderate Degree	3.23	Moderate Degree
2. Parents/guardians did not return outputs on time.	3.21	Moderate Degree	3.19	Moderate Degree
3. Modules were not returned the same way it was distributed.	3.29	Moderate Degree	3.23	Moderate Degree
4. Modules were in bad condition upon retrieval.	3.13	Moderate Degree	3.27	Moderate Degree
5. Parents/ guardians did not follow the minimum health	3.04	Moderate	3.08	Moderate

6.	protocol in returning the modules. Learners did not answer some of the activities in the module.	3.38	Degree Moderate Degree	3.31	Degree Moderate Degree
7.	The teacher did not follow up with the learners whose modules were not returned on time.	2.83	Moderate Degree	2.85	Moderate Degree
8.	Parents/ guardians did not follow classroom procedures set by the teacher/adviser in returning the modules.	2.92	Moderate Degree	3.08	Moderate Degree
9.	The teacher did not disinfect the modules upon retrieval.	3.13	Moderate Degree	2.88	Moderate Degree
10.	There is a fear that the module is contaminated with Covid-19 upon retrieval	3.42	Moderate Degree	3.19	Moderate Degree
	Sub-mean	3.14	Moderate Degree	3.13	Moderate Degree

Table 3 shows the degree of challenges encountered by teachers on modular learning in the area of retrieval when grouped according to age. Item no. 10 got the highest mean score of 3.42 in the younger group, while item no. 4, got the highest mean score of 3.27 for the older group. Both are interpreted as "moderate degree." The overall mean score for the younger group is 3.14, while the overall mean score for the older group is 3.13, and both are interpreted as "moderate degree." This means that teachers are concerned with the condition of the modules during the retrieval, most especially with the threat that the modules were contaminated with the virus. (McCallum 2020) in her article discussed that coronavirus can stay on a surface for hours or even several days.

Table 4

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Teachers on Modular Learning in the Area of Feedback Giving When Grouped According to Age

Areas	Younger		Older		
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	
C. Feedback Giving					
1.	Parents/guardians were not active in asking questions about the module.	2.96	Moderate Degree	3.35	Moderate Degree
2.	Parents/guardians did not inform the teacher of their learners' progress.	3.17	Moderate Degree	3.31	Moderate Degree
3.	Parents/guardians did not attend homeroom PTA meetings.	2.88	Moderate Degree	3.15	Moderate Degree
4.	Parents/guardians did not ask the teacher for clarifications about certain topics in the module.	3.17	Moderate Degree	3.08	Moderate Degree
5.	Parents/guardians and the learners did not ask the teacher about unclear topics in the module.	3.50	High Degree	3.00	Moderate Degree
6.	Modules were not answered by the learners by themselves.	3.42	Moderate Degree	3.38	Moderate Degree
7.	Parents/guardians did not raise concerns about contracting covid 19 during the distribution and retrieval of the module.	3.54	High Degree	3.46	Moderate Degree
8.	Parents/guardians had difficulty explaining the lessons to the learners.	3.58	High Degree	3.62	High Degree
9.	Parents/guardians complained about the schedule of the distribution and retrieval of modules.	3.00	Moderate Degree	3.31	Moderate Degree
10.	Parents/guardians did not discuss with the teacher about intervention strategies to strengthen their child's learning.	3.25	Moderate Degree	3.50	High Degree
	Sub-mean	3.25	Moderate Degree	3.32	Moderate Degree

Table 4 shows the degree of challenges encountered by teachers on modular learning in the area of feedback giving when grouped according to age. Item no. 8, got the highest mean score of 3.58 in the younger group and 3.62 for the older group. Both are interpreted as "high degree." The overall mean score for the younger group is 3.25, while the overall mean score for the older group is 3.32, and both are interpreted as "moderate degree." This means that teachers are really concerned with how the parents/guardians assist their children with their lessons. It shows that parents/guardians need to be equipped with the proper knowledge to help their children with their lessons. (Azubuike and Aina 2020) in their article states that parents carry the responsibility as a teacher to their children during the time of pandemic. They found out that a number of parents who didn't know

how to support their children's learning were those who gained secondary education or lower, and those parents who said that they didn't have time to support their children's learning were those parents who graduated college.

Table 5
Degree of Challenges Encountered by Teachers on Modular Learning in the Area of Distribution When Grouped According to Sex

Areas	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
A. Distribution				
1. Modules were not readily available for teachers to download.	3.18	Moderate Degree	3.18	Moderate Degree
2. Adequate funds were not provided in preparing the modules.	3.06	Moderate Degree	3.18	Moderate Degree
3. Materials for printing the modules were not enough.	2.88	Moderate Degree	3.00	Moderate Degree
4. Insufficient time was given to print the modules.	2.88	Moderate Degree	3.15	Moderate Degree
5. Not enough modules were produced for distribution.	3.12	Moderate Degree	2.97	Moderate Degree
6. Parents/ guardians did not observe minimum health protocols during module distribution.	2.76	Moderate Degree	3.12	Moderate Degree
7. Parents/guardians did not pick up modules on time.	3.29	Moderate Degree	3.24	Moderate Degree
8. Parents/guardians lack interest in picking up the modules.	3.06	Moderate Degree	2.97	Moderate Degree
9. Parents/ guardians did not follow room procedures prepared by the teacher in distributing the modules.	3.18	Moderate Degree	3.03	Moderate Degree
10. Modules were not disinfected before distribution.	3.06	Moderate Degree	3.18	Moderate Degree
Sub-mean	3.05	Moderate Degree	3.10	Moderate Degree

Table 5 shows the degree of challenges teachers encounter on modular learning in the distribution area when grouped according to sex. Item no. 7, got the highest mean score of 3.29 in the male group and 3.24 for the female group. Both are interpreted as "moderate degree." The overall mean score for the male group is 3.05, while the overall mean score for the female group is 3.10, and both are interpreted as "moderate degree." With this data, parents/ guardians are having a hard time getting the modules on time, and it gave a challenge to teachers because it affects the time given for the learners to answer the module.

Table 6
Degree of Challenges Encountered by Teachers on Modular Learning in the Area of Retrieval When Grouped According to Sex

Areas	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
B. Retrieval				
1. Parents/guardians did not return the modules on time.	3.29	Moderate Degree	3.09	Moderate Degree
2. Parents/guardians did not return outputs on time.	3.35	Moderate Degree	3.12	Moderate Degree
3. Modules were not returned the same way it was distributed.	3.53	High Degree	3.12	Moderate Degree
4. Modules were in bad condition upon retrieval.	3.47	Moderate Degree	3.06	Moderate Degree
5. Parents/ guardians did not follow the minimum health protocol in returning the modules.	3.12	Moderate Degree	3.03	Moderate Degree
6. Learners did not answer some of the activities in the module.	3.47	Moderate Degree	3.27	Moderate Degree
7. The teacher did not follow up with the learners whose modules were not returned on time.	2.71	Moderate Degree	2.91	Moderate Degree
8. Parents/ guardians did not follow classroom procedures set by the teacher/adviser in returning the modules.	2.88	Moderate Degree	3.06	Moderate Degree
9. The teacher did not disinfect the modules upon	2.94	Moderate	3.03	Moderate

retrieval.				
10. There is a fear that the module is contaminated with Covid-19 upon retrieval	3.65	Degree High Degree	3.12	Degree Moderate Degree
Sub-mean	3.24	Moderate Degree	3.08	Moderate Degree

Table 6 shows the degree of challenges encountered by teachers on modular learning in the area of retrieval when grouped according to sex. Item no. 10, got the highest mean score of 3.65 in the male group and was interpreted as "high degree." Meanwhile, item no. 6, which states, "Learners did not answer some of the activities in the module," got the highest mean score of 3.27 in the female group and was interpreted as a "moderate degree." The overall mean score for the male group is 3.24, while the overall mean score for the female group is 3.08, and both are interpreted as "moderate degree." This means that teachers are really concerned with the threat of virus transmissions during the retrieval of the module, and based on the data, if learners do not answer some of the activities on the module, it may lead to lower learner performance.

Table 7
Degree of Challenges Encountered by Teachers on Modular Learning in the Area of Feedback Giving When Grouped According to Sex

Areas	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
C. Feedback Giving				
1. Parents/guardians were not active in asking questions about the module.	3.18	Moderate Degree	3.15	Moderate Degree
2. Parents/guardians did not inform the teacher of their learners' progress.	3.00	Moderate Degree	3.36	Moderate Degree
3. Parents/guardians did not attend homeroom PTA meetings.	2.71	Moderate Degree	3.18	Moderate Degree
4. Parents/guardians did not ask the teacher for clarifications about certain topics in the module.	2.88	Moderate Degree	3.24	Moderate Degree
5. Parents/guardians and the learners did not ask the teacher about unclear topics in the module.	3.12	Moderate Degree	3.30	Moderate Degree
6. Modules were not answered by the learners by themselves.	3.29	Moderate Degree	3.45	Moderate Degree
7. Parents/guardians did not raise concerns about contracting covid 19 during the distribution and retrieval of the module.	3.47	Moderate Degree	3.52	High Degree
8. Parents/guardians had difficulty in explaining the lessons to the learners.	3.59	High Degree	3.61	High Degree
9. Parents/guardians complained about the schedule of the distribution and retrieval of modules.	3.24	Moderate Degree	3.12	Moderate Degree
10. Parents/guardians did not discuss with the teacher about intervention strategies to strengthen their child's learning.	3.18	Moderate Degree	3.48	Moderate Degree
Sub-mean	3.16	Moderate Degree	3.34	Moderate Degree

Table 7 shows the degree of challenges encountered by teachers on modular learning in the area of feedback giving when grouped according to sex. Item no. 8, got the highest mean score of 3.59 in the male group and 3.61 for the female group. Both are interpreted as "high degree." The overall mean score for the male group is 3.16, while the overall mean score for the female group is 3.34, and both are interpreted as "moderate degree." This means that there is a lack of knowledge for the parents/guardians in assisting their learners in their lessons. There must be proper orientation and guidance to the parents/ guardians so that they can explain well to their learners about the lessons.

Table 8
Degree of Challenges Encountered by Teachers on Modular Learning in the Area of Distribution When Grouped According to Length of Service

Areas	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
A. Distribution				
1. Modules were not readily available for teachers to download.	3.40	Moderate Degree	3.07	Moderate Degree
2. Adequate funds were not provided in preparing the	3.09	Moderate	3.19	Moderate

modules.				
3. Materials for printing the modules were not enough.	3.00	Degree Moderate Degree	2.93	Degree Moderate Degree
4. Insufficient time was given to print the modules.	3.17	Moderate Degree	2.96	Moderate Degree
5. Not enough modules were produced for distribution.	3.13	Moderate Degree	2.93	Moderate Degree
6. Parents/ guardians did not observe minimum health protocols during module distribution.	3.09	Moderate Degree	2.93	Moderate Degree
7. Parents/guardians did not pick up modules on time.	3.30	Moderate Degree	3.22	Moderate Degree
8. Parents/guardians lack interest in picking up the modules.	3.13	Moderate Degree	2.89	Moderate Degree
9. Parents/ guardians did not follow room procedures prepared by the teacher in distributing the modules.	3.17	Moderate Degree	3.00	Moderate Degree
10. Modules were not disinfected before distribution.	3.30	Moderate Degree	3.00	Moderate Degree
Sub-mean	3.17	Moderate Degree	3.01	Moderate Degree

Table 8 shows the degree of challenges encountered by teachers on modular learning in the area of distribution when grouped according to length of service. Item no. 1, got the highest mean score of 3.40 in the lower group and was interpreted as "moderate degree." Item no. 2, got the highest mean score of 3.19 in the higher group and was interpreted as a "moderate degree." The overall mean score for the lower group is 3.17, while the overall mean score for the higher group is 3.01, and both are interpreted as "moderate degree." This means that there is a lack of preparation in terms of module availability and funds for the distribution of the module.

Table 9

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Teachers on Modular Learning in the Area of Retrieval When Grouped According to Length of Service

Areas	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
B. Retrieval				
1. Parents/guardians did not return the modules on time.	3.22	Moderate Degree	3.11	Moderate Degree
2. Parents/guardians did not return outputs on time.	3.39	Moderate Degree	3.04	Moderate Degree
3. Modules were not returned the same way it was distributed.	3.43	Moderate Degree	3.11	Moderate Degree
4. Modules were in bad condition upon retrieval.	3.22	Moderate Degree	3.19	Moderate Degree
5. Parents/ guardians did not follow the minimum health protocol in returning the modules.	3.04	Moderate Degree	3.07	Moderate Degree
6. Learners did not answer some of the activities in the module.	3.30	Moderate Degree	3.37	Moderate Degree
7. The teacher did not follow up with the learners whose modules were not returned on time.	2.87	Moderate Degree	2.81	Moderate Degree
8. Parents/ guardians did not follow classroom procedures set by the teacher/adviser in returning the modules.	3.00	Moderate Degree	3.00	Moderate Degree
9. The teacher did not disinfect the modules upon retrieval.	3.13	Moderate Degree	2.89	Moderate Degree
10. There is a fear that the module is contaminated with Covid-19 upon retrieval	3.30	Moderate Degree	3.30	Moderate Degree
Sub-mean	3.19	Moderate Degree	3.09	Moderate Degree

Table 9 shows the degree of challenges encountered by teachers on modular learning in the area of retrieval when grouped according to length of service. Item no. 3, got the highest mean score of 3.43 in the lower group and was interpreted as "moderate degree." Item no. 6, which states, got the highest mean score of 3.37 in the higher group and was interpreted as "moderate degree." The overall mean score for the lower group is 3.19, while the overall mean score for the higher group is 3.09, and both are interpreted as "moderate degree." With this data, this means that teachers are concerned with the condition of the module upon retrieval. Modules were not

arranged the same way as how it was distributed, and it may cause confusion to the next holder of the module. Teachers are also concerned with learners not answering some of the activities of the modules.

Table 10
Degree of Challenges Encountered by Teachers on Modular Learning in the Area of Feedback Giving When Grouped According to Length of Service

Areas	Lower	Interpretation	Higher	Interpretation
	Mean		Mean	
C. Feedback Giving				
1. Parents/guardians were not active in asking questions about the module.	3.00	Moderate Degree	3.30	Moderate Degree
2. Parents/guardians did not inform the teacher of their learners' progress.	3.22	Moderate Degree	3.26	Moderate Degree
3. Parents/guardians did not attend homeroom PTA meetings.	3.00	Moderate Degree	3.04	Moderate Degree
4. Parents/guardians did not ask the teacher for clarifications about certain topics in the module.	3.09	Moderate Degree	3.15	Moderate Degree
5. Parents/guardians and the learners did not ask the teacher about unclear topics in the module.	3.35	Moderate Degree	3.15	Moderate Degree
6. Modules were not answered by the learners by themselves.	3.39	Moderate Degree	3.41	Moderate Degree
7. Parents/guardians did not raise concerns about contracting covid 19 during the distribution and retrieval of the module.	3.52	High Degree	3.48	Moderate Degree
8. Parents/guardians had difficulty explaining the lessons to the learners.	3.43	Moderate Degree	3.74	High Degree
9. Parents/guardians complained about the schedule of the distribution and retrieval of modules.	3.09	Moderate Degree	3.22	Moderate Degree
10. Parents/guardians did not discuss with the teacher about intervention strategies to strengthen their child's learning.	3.13	Moderate Degree	3.59	High Degree
Sub-mean	3.22	Moderate Degree	3.33	Moderate Degree

Table 10 shows the degree of challenges encountered by teachers on modular learning in the area of feedback giving when grouped according to length of service. Item no. 7 got the highest mean score of 3.52 in the lower group and was interpreted as a "high degree." Item no. 8, got the highest mean score of 3.74 in the higher group and was interpreted as "high degree." The overall mean score for the lower group is 3.22, while the overall mean score for the higher group is 3.33, and both are interpreted as "moderate degree." This means that proper instructions and proper knowledge were not properly given by the parents/ guardians to their learners. There must be intervention when the parents/ guardians do not properly explain lessons to their learners because it may lead to learners' low academic performance.

Table 11
Difference in the Degree of Challenges Encountered by Teachers on Modular Learning in the Area of Distribution When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger (below 41 yrs old)	24	23.29	259.00	0.301	0.05	Not Significant
	Older (41 yrs old and above)	26	27.54				
Sex	Male	17	23.68	249.50	0.524	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	33	26.44				
Length of Service	Shorter (below 12 years)	23	23.61	286.50	0.639	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer (12 years and above)	27	27.11				

Table 11 shows the difference in the degree of challenges encountered by teachers on modular learning in the area of distribution when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. When grouped according to age, the younger group has a mean rank of 23.29 and 27.54 for the older group, the computed Mann-Whitney U test was 259.00, and the p -value was 0.301. It is higher than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "not significant." When grouped according to sex, the male group has a mean score of 26.68 and 26.44 for the female group, the computed Mann-Whitney U test was 249.50, and the p -value was 0.524, which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "not significant." When grouped according to the length of service, the shorter group has a mean score of 23.61 and 27.11 for the longer group; the computed Mann-Whitney U test was 286.50, and the p -value was 0.639, which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "not significant." Thus, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the degree of challenges encountered by teachers on modular learning in the area of distribution when grouped and compared according to the age, sex, and length of service" was hereby "accepted." Regardless of whether the teachers are young or old, male or female, longer or shorter in service, they face the same challenges.

Table 12

Significant Difference in the Degree of Challenges Encountered by Teachers on Modular Learning in the Area of Retrieval When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	p -value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger (below 41 yrs old)	24	25.88	303.00	0.861	0.05	Not Significant
	Older (41 yrs old and above)	26	25.15				
Sex	Male	17	27.76	242.00	0.429	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	33	24.33				
Length of Service	Shorter (below 12 years)	23	26.57	286.00	0.633	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer (12 years and above)	27	24.59				

Table 12 shows the comparative analysis of the degree of challenges encountered by teachers on modular learning in the area of retrieval when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. When grouped according to age, the younger group has a mean score of 25.88 and 25.25 for the older group, the computed Mann-Whitney U test was 303.00, and the p -value was 0.861, which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "not significant." When grouped according to sex, the male group has a mean score of 27.76 and 24.33 for the female group, the computed Mann-Whitney U test was 242.00, and the p -value was 0.429, which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "not significant." When grouped according to the length of service, the shorter group has a mean score of 26.57 and 24.59 for the longer group; the computed Mann-Whitney U test was 286.00, and the p -value was 0.633, which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "not significant." Thus, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the degree of challenges encountered by teachers on modular learning in the area of retrieval when grouped and compared according to the age, sex, and length of service" was hereby "accepted." The result shows that age, sex, and length of service show no significant difference in the degree of challenges encountered by teachers on modular learning in the area of retrieval when grouped and compared according to age, sex, and length of service.

Table 13

Significant Difference in the Degree of Challenges Encountered by Teachers on Modular Learning in the Area of Feedback Giving When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	p -value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger (below 41 yrs old)	24	24.21	281.00	0.546	0.05	Not Significant
	Older (41 yrs old and above)	26	26.69				

Sex	Male	17	22.29	226.00	0.263	Not Significant
	Female	33	27.15			
Length of Service	Shorter (below 12 years)	23	23.61	267.00	0.395	Not Significant
	Longer (12 years and above)	27	27.11			

Table 13 shows the comparative analysis of the degree of challenges encountered by teachers on modular learning in the area of feedback giving when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. When grouped according to age, the younger group has a mean score of 24.21 and 26.69 for the older group, the computed Mann-Whitney U test was 281.00, and the p -value was 0.546, which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "not significant." When grouped according to sex, the male group has a mean score of 22.29 and 27.15 for the female group, the computed Mann-Whitney U test was 226.00, and the p -value was 0.263, which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "not significant." When grouped according to the length of service, the shorter group has a mean score of 23.61 and 27.11 for the longer group; the computed Mann-Whitney U test was 267.00, and the p -value was 0.395, which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "not significant." Thus, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the degree of challenges encountered by teachers on modular learning in the area of feedback giving when grouped and compared according to the age, sex, and length of service" was hereby "accepted." The result shows that age, sex, and length of service show no significant difference in the degree of challenges encountered by teachers on modular learning in the area of feedback giving when grouped and compared according to age, sex, and length of service.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the degree of challenges teachers encountered in modular learning based on distribution, retrieval, and feedback-giving was moderate. From this finding, it can be concluded that teachers are having problems with modular learning, especially since this was the first time in the history of DepEd Negros Oriental that this had been adopted. The degree of challenges teachers encountered in modular learning when grouped into ages was moderate. It can be concluded that the younger and the older age group has similar challenges encountered in modular learning. Teachers were concerned that parents/ guardians did not pick up the modules on time. The degree of challenges teachers encountered in modular learning when grouped by sex was moderate. With this finding, it can be concluded that teachers are having problems, especially during module retrieval. Teachers were worried that the virus might contaminate the modules returned. Teachers are also concerned with how the modules were returned. Some of the modules were not returned the way it was distributed, which may lead to confusion for the next module holder. The degree of challenges teachers encountered in modular learning when grouped by length of service was moderate. Regardless of the length of service, the levels of challenges of teachers are the same at a moderate degree. Teachers are concerned with parents/ guardians having difficulty explaining the lessons to their learners. Such a problem can cause a decline in academic performance in the learners, or worse; the learners will be taught false or wrong information about the given module. Out of the results of the study, this paper calls for the following: 1) teachers must be given enough time and funds to prepare the learning materials and consider the kind of community where the learners belong to since some live in the most remote area; 2) parents/ guardians must be properly equipped with the proper knowledge of the lessons; 3) teachers must be given enough supply of disinfectant and enough time to disinfect the modules; 4) teachers must give positive motivation to the parents/ guardians to return the modules on time to avoid confusion and delay; and 5) immediate problems like the fear of contamination of the virus must be addressed. An annual development plan must be developed for the immediate problem, and a 3-year development plan must be made to address the pressing problems of modular learning.

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References

- Acosta, M. (2016, May 28). Retrieved September 2020, from SCAD Independent.Org: <https://journal.scad-independent.org/index.php/jipeuradeun/article/view/94/163>
- Campus Explorer. (n.d.). Different Types of Distance Learning. Retrieved September 2020, from Campus Explorer: <https://www.campusexplorer.com/college-advice-tips/7021E31E/Different-Types-of-Distance-Learning/>
- DepEd Regional Office 3. (2020, July 7). Modular learning preferred by CL learners; DepEd prepares Self-Learning Modules for education's new normal. Retrieved December 2020, from <https://region3.deped.gov.ph/modular-learning-preferred-by-cl-learners-deped-prepares-self-learning-modules-for-educations-new-normal/>
- Eliver, A., Abule, A., Cornel, M., & Maguate, G. (2023). Teachers research Perception, competence and Work Performance: Basis for A Capability Building Plan. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM)*, 11(10), 42-73.
- Fidalgo, P., Thormann, J., Kulyk, O., & Lencastre, J. (2020, May 20). Students' perceptions on distance education: A multinational study. Retrieved September 2020, from Springer Link: https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s41239-020-00194-2?utm_source=getftr
- Fulgencio, R. G., & Maguate, G. (2023). Awareness and Implementation of the Public Elementary School Teachers of the Positive Discipline Model: Basis for a Guidance program. *International Journal of Latest Research in Humanities and Social Science (IJLRHSS)*, 6(08), 41-61.
- Folsom, J. (2020, April 11). Distance Learning During the COVID-19 Pandemic. Retrieved September 2020, from WestEd: <https://www.wested.org/wested-insights/distance-learning-during-the-covid-19-pandemic/#>
- Jayme, R., & Maguate, G. (2023). Issues and Concerns of Teachers towards Modular Distance Learning Approach. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM)*, 11(08), 2848-2857.
- Joyce, L. (2020, January 16). Stackable, Modular Learning: Education Built for the Future of Work. Retrieved December 2020, from Edx: <https://blog.edx.org/stackable-modular-learning-education-built-future-work>
- Markova, T., Glazkova, I., & Zaborova, E. (2017, February 21). Quality Issues of Online Distance Learning. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877042817300435>
- Mean-Chin, M. (2020, October 11). Students' New Normal : Modular Distance Learning . <https://www.uniquephilippines.com/students-new-normal-modular-distance-learning/>
- Mitrofanova, Y., Filippova, O., Gudkova, S., & Ivanova, E. (2020, June 8). Quality Assessment of Modular Educational Resources for Smart Education System. Retrieved December 2020, from Springer Link: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-981-15-5584-8_43
- Ohoylan, J. G. D., & Maguate, G. (2023). TikTok: Undistressing Tool for Teachers. *International Journal of Latest Research in Humanities and Social Science (IJLRHSS)*, 6(07), 149-155.
- Macapagong, E., Maguate, G., & Geroso, M. J. S. (2023). Living and Teaching Internationally: Teachers' Experiences, Prospects and Challenges. *Valley International Journal Digital Library*, 2882-2894.
- Omonovich, K., Kamildjanovna, K., Nurmukhamadovna, K., & Qambaraliyeva, D. (2020, March 18). THE USE OF MODULAR TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION. Retrieved December 2020, from *Journal of Critical Reviews*: <http://jcreview.com/fulltext/197-1587300208.pdf?1608968832>
- Pasique, D. A., & Maguate, G. (2023). Challenges And Opportunitites Among Educators in The Implementation of Continuing Professional Development. *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research (IJFMR)*, 5(4).
- Pozdnyakova, O., & Pozdnyakov, A. (2017). Adult Students' Problems in the Distance Learning. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877705817301054>
- Sadeghi, M. (2019, March 20). A Shift from Classroom to Distance Learning: Advantages and Limitations. Retrieved September 2020, from *International Journal of Research in English*: http://ijreeonline.com/files/site1/user_files_68bcd6/sadeghi92-A-10-156-1-48ab29c.pdf
- Salutin, M. A., & Maguate, G. (2023). Values-Based Exercises for the Development of Reading Readiness Skills for Preschool Children. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM)*, 11(08), 22-30.

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